

ABSTRACT BOOK

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ORAL PRESENTATIONS

EXPOSURE TO INDOOR AIR POLLUTION AND ABSENTEEISM SCHOOLCHILDREN

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OBJECTIVES: Beside air pollution in urban outdoor settings, indoor air can also be contaminated, both from outdoor and indoor sources.

Exposure to indoor air pollution may lead to very serious health effects, especially on the respiratory system. The aim of this study was to estimate the effects of indoor air pollutants on children's health and school absenteeism.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: Anamnestic retrospective study was done on 1074 children aged between 7 and 11 in Nis.

An original questionnaire was used in an interview between trained physicians and children's parents in the period from February to June 2005. Interview data were processed using Epiinfo 6.

RESULTS: It was found that exposure to combustion by-products led to children's respiratory and nonspecific symptoms. Parental smoking was associated with wheezing, bronchitis, headache and fatigue. Children who were exposed to passive smoking and the smoke from heating materials had higher number of physician visits due to respiratory problems ($\chi^2=8.72$; $p < 0.05$) and more frequent school absenteeism due to illness ($\chi^2=10.15$; $p < 0.005$) than children not exposed to these environmental risk factors.

CONCLUSION: In conclusion indoor air pollution affects children's health and increases their school absenteeism.

KEY WORDS: indoor air pollution, schoolchildren, respiratory system, disease, absenteeism

ENVIRONMENTAL NOISE ANNOYANCE OF THE POPULATION OF NOVI SAD FOR THE PERIOD 2006–2017

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OBJECTIVE: The percentage of highly annoyed population may be determined by modeling data of measured noise levels or by interviewing the population. Both methods have limits, but provide the insight into the relationship between environmental noise and health.

METHOD: During the 2006–2017, Institute for Public Health of Vojvodina conducted 3 surveys in accor-

dance with the standardized survey ISO/TS 15666:2003. The surveys were done among the adult population, the first in 2006, the second in 2012, and the third in 2017. The surveys covered 31 questions for respondents, related to noise-induced annoyance and the individual reactions to noise. Respondents living nearby the noise measuring points in Novi Sad were randomly selected.

RESULTS: The investigated population is annoyed by traffic noise (47-59%), construction works (25%-32%), noise from the neighborhood (25%-27%), noise from the catering and other facilities (12-24%) and noise from elevators and installations in residential buildings (11-15%). Due to traffic noise, 13%-46% of respondents would change their apartments. Environmental noise annoyed people watching TV (13%-78%), resting during the day-time period (30%-60%) and mental work (36-56%). Also, based on research, 6% of respondents aged

18-25 years and 51% of respondents older than 65, wake up at night because of traffic noise.

CONCLUSION: The results of long-term environmental noise measurements and conducted surveys in Novi Sad confirm that urban noise mostly originates from road traffic and seriously disturbs people.

KEYWORDS: Environmental noise, Environmental Exposure, Population, Health

ANKETIRANJE STANOVNIŠTVA O UZNEMIRENOSTI BUKOM IZ ŽIVOTNE SREDINE U NOVOM SADU, 2006-2017

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OBJECTIVE: Buka iz životne sredine uznemirava izloženo stanovništvo. Procenat stanovništva uznemirenog bukom se odeređuje modelovanjem, korišćenjem podataka o izmerenom nivou buke, ili neposredno, stanovništvo se anketira, odnosno pojedinci odgovaraju na pitanje da li im i kakva im buka koliko smeta. I jedan i drugi način određivanja procenta stanovništva uznemirenog bukom, jasno, imaju brojnih ograničenja, ali ipak pružaju uvid u to koliko buka iz životne sredine zaista utiče na živote ljudi.

METHOD: Institut za javno zdravlje Vojvodine (IZJZV) je tokom perioda 2006 - 2017 sproveo tri anketna ispitivanja, u skladu sa standardizovanim upitnikom ISO/TS 15666:2003. Ispitivanja su obuhvatila 31 pitanje za ispitanike vezano za subjektivni doživljaj buke i subjektivnu procenu uticaja buke na zdravlje ljudi, istovremeno sa merenjem i utvrđivanjem nivoa buke u životnoj sredini, a uzorak ispitanika je izabran metodom slučajnog izbora prema adresama mernih mesta za merenje nivoa buke u životnoj sredini. Prvo anketiranje je obavljeno među odraslom populacijom 2006. godine, drugo 2012. godine, a treće 2017. godine.

RESULTS: Istraživanja su omogućila sagledavanje subjektivnog doživljaja buke kao činioca iz životne sredine

koga je nemoguće izbeći, a koji dovodi do uznemirenosti stanovništva. Izdvojeni su neki od rezultata ispitivanja, koji variraju u zavisnosti od godine istraživanja i ispitivane populacije. Procenat ispitanika koji bi zbog saobraćajne buke menjali stan kreće se u rasponu 13%-46%. Buka ljude najčešće ometa pri gledanju televizije (13%-78%), dnevnom odmoru (30%-60%) i mentalnom radu (36-56%), a najviše ih uznemirava buka poreklom od saobraćaja (47-59%) i građevinskih radova (25%-32%), buka iz komšiluka (25%-27%), buka koju stvaraju ugostiteljski objekti u okruženju (12-24%) i buka od lifova i instalacija u stambenim zgradama (11-15%). Takođe, noću se zbog saobraćajne buke budi 6% studenata, odnosno 51% ispitanika starijih od 65 godina. Sumarno, oko 50% stanovništva se izjašnjava da je veoma uznemireno bukom i tokom dana i tokom noći.

CONCLUSION: Rezultati višegodišnjih merenja buke u životnoj sredini Grada Novog Sada i anketnih ispitivanja stanovništva potvrđuju da buka iz urbane životne sredine, koja je najvećim delom poreklom od drumskog saobraćaja, uznemirava ljude i predstavlja dugotrajno prisutnu opasnost po zdravlje ljudi.

KEYWORDS: Environmental noise, Environmental Exposure, Population, Health

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVE SUBSTANCES IN THE WATER SUPPLY SYSTEM OF URBAN ECOSYSTEM

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BACKGROUND: Pharmacological active substances (PAS) are complex molecules with very different functional, physical - chemical and biological properties. Numerous

researches, which have been carried out in different parts of Europe and in the USA have shown the presence of PAS in waste and surface waters, in underground water